

Meaty flavour tonalities by Maillard reaction

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Abstract

Existing studies reveal that meat flavours from different animal species, although different in tonality, have many aroma molecules in common. Accordingly, we found that from a limited set of starting materials, it is possible to obtain different tonalities of flavour by using different ratios of the materials. Moreover, by changing reaction conditions like pH, time, and temperature one can tune to chicken direction applying a lower temperature. At higher temperature, a beef direction could only be found at a narrower pH interval, around 6.0. Presently this understanding is used to develop natural meaty flavourings based on non-meat foodstuff.

Keywords: Maillard, model reaction, chicken, beef, roast

Introduction

To increase sustainability, meat consumption should be reduced by use of vegetable-based meat replacers with similar nutritional value like Vegetarian Butcher products. These meat replacers however lack the specific precursors for the Maillard reaction responsible for meaty aromas and flavours and need to be flavoured to give the full meat impression. To avoid the use of meat based ingredients, the most efficient applied meaty flavours should be based on Maillard reactions of non-meat ingredients only. These flavours are made on an industrial scale but getting high quality natural vegan flavours remains a challenge. Formation of specific meat flavours of different tonalities should reflect chicken / beef / pork identity and cooking process like boiling / oven / roasting. A natural flavouring preparation should be based on foodstuff ingredients only and traditional processing as laid down in EU regulation [1]. For better understanding to get these meat flavourings tonalities from natural sourced ingredients, reactions with pure substances were evaluated on potential to get different meat tonalities.

Fresh raw meat has a very bland flavour. Only upon cooking the meat, the flavours related to specific animal species (chicken / beef / pork etc.) as well as those reflecting the cooking process (boiling / oven / roasting etc.) are formed. These Maillard reaction flavours originate from a similar set of reducing sugars ribose, glucose and amino acids *e.g.* glycine, cysteine for most animal species. Most of the aroma molecules are formed from Maillard intermediates from amino acid and reducing sugars reaction resulting in reactive semi transient species as diketosugars (oxosones). These react further in sugar degradation products like acetoin, but reaction with amino acids gives also ammoniac and hydrogen sulphide resulting in a complex mixture with Strecker aldehydes *e.g.* isobutyraldehydes, heterocyclic compounds *e.g.* furans, thiophenes and pyrazines besides some thiols and polymeric substances like melanoidins [2].

A meaty flavouring by Maillard reaction was reported by reaction of cysteine with a reducing sugar source [3] also in combination with thiamine [4] and / or fat [5], and more recently in a complex multistep method [6].

Mechanistic work with ¹³C labelled precursors demonstrated that some of the important meaty volatiles are formed from especially the combination of cysteine, thiamine and xylose, but 2-methyl-3-furanthiol and 3-mercapto-2-pentanone can also be derived from thiamine itself, while for others thiamine did not play a role as precursor [7]. Common understanding is that release of H₂S is key for meat flavour formation in the Maillard reaction [8, 9]. Levels of cysteine as H₂S source are much higher in non-meat sources (*e.g.* cabbage, onion with about 1000 ppm) than levels of thiamine (peas and soy with about 1 ppm) [10, 11]. Hence, we focussed on model studies to produce different meat tonalities formed by cysteine (or other sulphur source) with reducing sugars as starting point and observed effect of thiamine and amino acid addition.

The Xylose / Cysteine system was chosen as model to prepare meaty flavours [12]. The work from Gasser and Grosch [13] indicates the same flavour molecules in both chicken and beef extracts to be present although in different ratios, *e.g.* 2-methylfuranthiol is much more abundant in chicken bouillon than in beef, while others were reported to have similar concentrations like furfurylthiol. Impact on the tonality of the flavours was studied by addition of other amino acids, thiamine, and sugars to the reaction mixture: *e.g.* β-alanine was reported to enhance the intensity of chicken and beef taste [14].

The type and intensity of volatiles formed in the Maillard reaction are strongly dependent on reaction conditions: pH, reaction time and temperature [15, 16]. Hence the obtained meat tonality from the model reaction was studied as a function of these parameters.

Experimental

The reaction ingredients β -alanine, cysteine.HCl, glycine, glucose, xylose, lactic acid and thiamine were purchased from SigmaAldrich. The model reaction mixtures was prepared by addition of 1 g xylose, 1 g of cysteine.HCl and 0.2 g lactic acid to 40 ml of water As indicated in Figure 1, optionally were added to the 40 ml reaction mixture: 1 g of glycine, 0.1 g of β -alanine, 0.2 g of thiamine and 1 g of glucose. By addition of 0.1 M of NaOH solution the pH was adjusted to pH = 6 for constant reaction conditions and pH 5, 6 and 7 upon variation of reaction conditions. The temperature was set to 95 °C with 4 hr reaction time for constant reaction conditions and varied from 75 °C to 95 °C with the reaction times between 4 and 8 hours as indicated in Table 1.

The mixture was placed in a 100 ml Duran glass bottle and heated in a hot air circulated oven. After cooling, sensory evaluation was done. Most reactions mixtures were found to be colourless except those prepared with β -alanine (Figure 2). Smell and taste were evaluated by 10x dilution into a 0.35% salt / 0.1% monosodium glutamate solution.

Results and discussion

Influence of amino acids and sugars

In Figure 1 experiments with several additions and ratios of amino acids and sugars are presented. A good meaty taste, *i.e.* pork-like, was observed when xylose and cysteine were combined and heated. Use of glycine addition enhanced the general meaty character. Upon trying several ratios and addition of glucose and β -alanine now clear chicken notes were obtained. Another ratio of ingredients and supplementing with a little thiamine on top gave more beefy notes. Hence it was confirmed that by variation of almost the same set of precursors, quite different flavours are formed by choosing different ratios, possibly giving similar flavour compounds, but at different ratios.

Figure 1: Different meaty profiles from different amino acids with xylose.

As shown in Figure 2 it was noticed that by addition of β -alanine colouring was much more intense. This can be explained from the higher reactivity of the amino acid group now in *beta* position and hence more remote from the carboxylate group. However, we found that this was not a determining factor to get more chicken or more beef type flavour.

Figure 2: A much darker colour is observed with addition of β -alanine.

Influence of pH, time and temperature in a statistical design of experiments (DOE)

To study the influence of reaction parameters as time, temperature and pH, a simple model system consisting of xylose and cysteine was used. Lactic acid, reported to be present in meat and contributing to taste, was used as acid. By choosing 3 levels of the three parameters, a full factorial design would have required 27 experiments (3 x 3 x 3) while the statistical screening design as shown in Table 1 allows for conclusions on the three parameters with only 9 experiments.

Table 1: Sensory results from reaction of Xylose, Cysteine and Lactic acid upon variation of reaction conditions pH, time and temperature.

Exp.N°	pH	Time (hr)	Temp (°C)	Smell	Taste
01	6	4	75	Sulphury	Chicken
02	7	8	75	No	Chicken
03	6	6	85	Sweet	Beef
04	6	8	95	Roast	Beef
05	5	4	95	No	No
06	5	6	75	Sulphury	Chicken
07	7	6	95	Sweet	Weak
08	7	4	85	No	No
09	5	8	85	Sweet	Sweet

From Table 1 the influence of Maillard reaction efficiency can be clearly observed. In Exp N° 03 and 04 a beef flavour is formed at high temperatures at pH 6. Chicken flavour could be observed at lower temperature (75°C) with no real dependence on pH or reaction time. For beef longer time at higher temperature in Exp N° 04 gave also more roast smell. The pH 6 seems critical at high temperature as at lower or higher pH no meat flavour is formed.

Conclusion

From a limited set of simple starting materials, it is possible to obtain different tonalities of meat flavour by using different ratios of the materials. Moreover, by changing reaction conditions like pH, time and temperature one can tune to chicken direction, but at higher temperature a beef direction seems only to be reached at a narrower pH interval, around 6.0. Presently this understanding is used to develop natural meaty flavourings based on non-meat foodstuff.

References

1. REGULATION (EC) No 1334/2008 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 16 December 2008 on flavorings and certain food ingredients with flavoring properties for use in and on foods and amending Council Regulation (EEC) No 1601/91, Regulations (EC) No 2232/96 and (EC) No 110/2008 and Directive 2000/13/EC.
2. Mathias K. Sucan and Deepthi K. Weerasinghe. Process and Reaction Flavors. In: ACS Symposium Series 905, Chapter 1, 1-13. ACS: Washington, DC 2005.
3. Morton I.D. Flavoring substances and their preparation. US2934437, 1960.
4. Bidmead D.S. Roasted meat flavor and process for producing same. US3394016, 1968.
5. Soeters, C.J. Process for preparing a savory meat flavoring. US3493395, 1970.
6. Blank I., Davidek T., Hofmann T., Schieberle P. Flavor active composition. US9005689 example 6, 2015.
7. Cerny C. Origin of carbons in sulfur-containing aroma compounds from the Maillard reaction of xylose, cysteine and thiamine. LWT - Food Sci Technol. 2007;40(8):1309-1315.
8. Kerler J. et al, Basic chemistry and process conditions for reaction flavors with particular focus on Maillard-type reactions. In: Food Flavor Technology: p 51, 2nd ed. 2010 Blackwell, Ed. Taylor & Linforth.
9. Jayasena D.D., Ahn D.U., Nam K.C., Jo C. Flavor Chemistry of Chicken Meat: A Review. Asian-Australas J Anim Sci. 2013;26(5):732-742.
10. Zurbruggen B.D. Onion and garlic biohydrolysates and their use as natural flavorings. WO01/30179,2001.
11. Walhqvist M. and Briggs. Water soluble vitamins, Chapter 16 Vitamin B-1 Food Charts Vegetables. In: on-line book Food Facts, : <http://apjcn.nhri.org.tw/server/info/books-phds/books/foodfacts/html> (by Visionary Voyager).
12. Cerny C. and Davidek T. Formation of Aroma Compounds from Ribose and Cysteine during the Maillard Reaction. J Agric Food Chem. 2003;51:2714-272.
13. Gasser U. and Grosch W. Primary odorants of chicken broth. A comparative study with meat broths from cow and ox. Z Lebensm Unters Forsch 1990;190:3-8.
14. Chen Y. and Ho C.T. Effects of Carnosine on Volatile Generation from Maillard Reaction of Ribose and Cysteine. J Agric Food Chem. 2002;50:2372.

15. Meynier A. and Mottram D.S. The effect of pH on the formation of volatile compounds in meat-related model systems. *Food Chem.* 1995;52:361-366.
16. Kwong G.Y., Hong, J.H., Kim Y.S., Lee S.M. and Kim K.O. Sensory characteristics and consumer acceptability of beef stock containing glutathione Maillard reaction products prepared at various conditions. *J. Food Sci.* 2011;76:51-57.